

BOUNDS ON THE OVERALL THERMOELASTIC MODULI

OF COMPOSITE MATERIALS

N. Laws
Department of Mathematics
Cranfield Institute of Technology
Cranfield, Bedford
England

Introduction

This paper is concerned with certain aspects of the problem of determining overall thermoelastic moduli for composite materials. In particular, attention is focused on the evaluation of bounds for the coefficients of thermal expansion and the heat capacities of general anisotropic materials composed of only two phases. It is shown for arbitrary isotropy that the required bounds may be obtained directly from known results in the mechanical problem. Further, it is shown how one can use the known self-consistent results in the mechanical problem to get corresponding results for the thermoelastic problem. In addition, it is proved that the self-consistent results always lie between the previously determined bounds. The paper continues with a discussion of the rather special case when the individual phases are isotropic. In other words, we consider those composites whose overall anisotropy is generated by geometry alone. Special cases of these results which are appropriate to isotropic dispersions of spheres, fibre reinforced materials, platelet reinforced materials and laminates are given explicitly. Previous work on the thermoelastic problem which has a direct bearing, to a greater or lesser extent, on this paper includes that of Levin (1), Schapery (2), Rosen and Hashin (3), Hashin (4), Laws (5,6) and Budiansky (7).

Preliminaries

We use the notation of Laws (5,6) which is just a slightly extended version of Hill's notation (8). Second order tensors are denoted by lower case letters with underlining, e.g. \underline{l} , \underline{g} , fourth order tensors are denoted by upper case letters, e.g. \underline{L} , \underline{M} , and scalars are denoted by lower case letters, e.g. α , c . All the second order tensors used in this paper are symmetric. The inner product of two second order tensors \underline{a} , \underline{b} is denoted by $\underline{a} \cdot \underline{b}$. In the usual suffix notation $\underline{a} \cdot \underline{b} = a_{ij} b_{ij}$. All the fourth order tensors have the symmetries

$$A_{ijkl} = A_{jikl} = A_{ijlk}.$$

The transpose of A is denoted by A^T and has components defined by

$$A^T_{ijkl} = A_{klij}.$$

The inverse, A^{-1} , of a non-singular fourth order tensor A satisfies the equations

$$A^{-1}A = I = AA^{-1},$$

where I is the unit tensor with components

$$I_{ijkl} = \frac{1}{2}(\delta_{ik} \delta_{jl} + \delta_{il} \delta_{jk}).$$

We now summarize the basic formulae of linear thermoelasticity. Let ψ_r , η_r respectively denote the Helmholtz free energy and entropy, per unit volume, at some point in the r th phase. Also let $\underline{\sigma}_r$ be the stress tensor and $\underline{\epsilon}_r$ be the linear strain tensor at the same point. We only consider materials at uniform temperature ($\theta_R + \theta$), where θ_R is a reference temperature. Then

$$\psi_r = \frac{1}{2} \underline{\epsilon}_r \cdot \underline{L} \underline{\epsilon}_r - \theta \underline{\epsilon}_r \cdot \underline{l}_r - \frac{1}{2} s_r(\epsilon) \theta^2 / \theta_R,$$

$$\underline{\sigma}_r = \underline{L}_r \underline{\epsilon}_r - \theta \underline{l}_r, \quad \eta_r = \underline{\epsilon}_r \cdot \underline{l}_r + s_r(\epsilon) \theta / \theta_R, \quad (1)$$

where $s_r(\epsilon)$ is the heat capacity, per unit volume, of the r th phase at constant strain. We note that there is an error of sign connected with the specific heats in the paper by Rosen and Hashin (3). It is often easier to work with the compliance tensor $\underline{M}_r = \underline{L}_r^{-1}$ rather than the stiffness tensor \underline{L}_r . Thus, we rewrite equations (1) in the form,

$$\underline{\epsilon}_r = \underline{M}_r \underline{\sigma}_r + \theta \underline{m}_r, \quad \eta_r = \underline{\sigma}_r \cdot \underline{m}_r + s_r(\sigma) \theta / \theta_R,$$

where

$$\bar{m}_r = M_r \bar{\ell}_r, \quad s_r(\sigma) = s_r(\varepsilon) + \theta_{Rr} \bar{\ell}_r \bar{m}_r.$$

Here $s_r(\sigma)$ is the heat capacity, per unit volume, of the r th phase at constant stress.

Overall Moduli

As usual in the theory of composite materials, we consider a representative volume R and let R_r denote that part of R which is occupied by the r th phase. The average of any quantity associated with the r th phase is the integral of that quantity over R_r divided by the volume of R_r . The overall average is obtained from the representative volume R itself. Thus, for example, the average stress in the r th phase is $\bar{\sigma}_r$ and the overall average is $\bar{\sigma}$. We denote the volume fraction of the r th phase by c_r . Since we only consider two phase composites we have $c_1 + c_2 = 1$, and, for example,

$$\bar{\sigma} = c_1 \bar{\sigma}_1 + c_2 \bar{\sigma}_2. \quad (2)$$

The starting point of this and other theoretical investigations is the assumption that

$$\bar{\varepsilon}_r = A_r \bar{\varepsilon} - \theta_r a_r, \quad (r = 1, 2), \quad (3)$$

where, for consistency, the concentration factors A_1, A_2, a_1, a_2 must satisfy

$$c_1 A_1 + c_2 A_2 = I, \quad c_1 a_1 + c_2 a_2 = Q. \quad (4)$$

From (2) and (3) we easily see that

$$\bar{\sigma} = L \bar{\varepsilon} - \theta \bar{\ell}, \quad (5)$$

where the overall tensors $L, \bar{\ell}$ are defined by

$$L = c_1 L_1 A_1 + c_2 L_2 A_2, \quad \bar{\ell} = c_1 (\bar{\ell}_1 + L_1 a_1) + c_2 (\bar{\ell}_2 + L_2 a_2). \quad (6)$$

Turning now to the thermostatics of composites, we quote the relevant results found by Laws (5):

$$L = L^T, \quad (7)$$

$$\bar{\ell} = c_1 A_1^T \bar{\ell}_1 + c_2 A_2^T \bar{\ell}_2, \quad (8)$$

$$\theta_R^{-1}(s(\epsilon) - c_1 s_1(\epsilon) - c_2 s_2(\epsilon)) = -c_1 a_1 \cdot \underline{l}_1 - c_2 a_2 \cdot \underline{l}_2. \quad (9)$$

Here, $s(\epsilon)$ is the overall heat capacity at constant strain. It is self-evident that the crucial step in the whole theory is the assumption of concentration factors for the phase average strains. Furthermore, there is no a priori reason to accord the strain tensor a status which is not enjoyed by the stress tensor. In analytic terms, there is just as much motivation for starting with the assumption

$$\underline{\bar{g}}_r = B_r \underline{\bar{g}} + \theta b_r \quad (r = 1, 2), \quad (10)$$

instead of (3). Happily, equations (10) are implied by the earlier analysis and a routine algebraic manipulation shows that

$$\underline{\bar{\epsilon}} = M \underline{\bar{\sigma}} + \theta \underline{m}, \quad (11)$$

$$\underline{m} = M \underline{l},$$

$$B_r = L_r A_r M, \quad b_r = B_r \underline{l} - \underline{l}_r - L_r a_r,$$

where $M = L^{-1}$. These relationships are significant because they show how the whole theory could have been based on equations (10) rather than equations (3). Furthermore, one can also show, see Laws (5), that

$$M = M^T, \quad (12)$$

$$\underline{m} = c_1 B_1^T \underline{m}_1 + c_2 B_2^T \underline{m}_2, \quad (13)$$

$$\theta_R^{-1}(s(\sigma) - c_1 s_1(\sigma) - c_2 s_2(\sigma)) = c_1 b_1 \cdot \underline{m}_1 + c_2 b_2 \cdot \underline{m}_2, \quad (14)$$

where $s(\sigma)$ is the overall heat capacity at constant stress. We remark that (12) - (14) could have been derived from the Gibbs energy function in the same way as (7) - (9) were derived from the Helmholtz energy function.

Up to this point, the fact that we only consider a two phase composite has not been decisive. Where the two phase composite differs from a general n -phase composite is that equations (4) and (6) may be solved to yield explicit formulae for the concentration factors as follows:

$$\begin{aligned}c_1 A_1 &= (L_1 - L_2)^{-1}(L - L_2), \\c_2 A_2 &= (L_2 - L_1)^{-1}(L - L_1),\end{aligned}\tag{15}$$

$$\begin{aligned}c_1 a_{11} &= (L_1 - L_2)^{-1}(\underline{\ell} - c_1 \underline{\ell}_1 - c_2 \underline{\ell}_2), \\c_2 a_{22} &= (L_2 - L_1)^{-1}(\underline{\ell} - c_1 \underline{\ell}_1 - c_2 \underline{\ell}_2).\end{aligned}\tag{16}$$

When (15) are substituted into (8) we find that

$$\underline{\ell} = (L - L_2)(L_1 - L_2)^{-1}\underline{\ell}_1 + (L - L_1)(L_2 - L_1)^{-1}\underline{\ell}_2.\tag{17}$$

Alternatively, from (17) we have

$$\underline{\ell} - c_1 \underline{\ell}_1 - c_2 \underline{\ell}_2 = (L - c_1 L_1 - c_2 L_2)(L_1 - L_2)^{-1}(\underline{\ell}_1 - \underline{\ell}_2),\tag{18}$$

in terms of deviations from the rule of mixtures. In addition, when we substitute (15) into (9) and make use of (18) we get

$$\begin{aligned}\theta_R^{-1}\{s(\epsilon) - c_1 s_1(\epsilon) - c_2 s_2(\epsilon)\} \\= (L_1 - L_2)^{-1}(\underline{\ell}_1 - \underline{\ell}_2) \cdot (c_1 L_1 + c_2 L_2 - L)(L_1 - L_2)^{-1}(\underline{\ell}_1 - \underline{\ell}_2).\end{aligned}\tag{19}$$

A similar calculation shows that the duals of (18) and (19) are

$$\underline{m} - c_1 \underline{m}_1 - c_2 \underline{m}_2 = (M - c_1 M_1 - c_2 M_2)(M_1 - M_2)^{-1}(\underline{m}_1 - \underline{m}_2),\tag{20}$$

$$\begin{aligned}\theta_R^{-1}\{s(\sigma) - c_1 s_1(\sigma) - c_2 s_2(\sigma)\} \\= (M_1 - M_2)^{-1}(\underline{m}_1 - \underline{m}_2) \cdot (M - c_1 M_1 - c_2 M_2)(M_1 - M_2)^{-1}(\underline{m}_1 - \underline{m}_2).\end{aligned}\tag{21}$$

Thus we have explicit formulae, (19) and (21), for the two overall heat capacities and two equivalent formulae, (18) and (20) for the overall coefficients of expansion. It turns out that it is easier to use (20) rather than (18). Since the purpose of this exercise is to predict information on the overall thermal moduli, we draw attention to an important feature of equations (19), (20) and (21). Indeed, a cursory examination shows that the right hand sides of these equations involve only the properties of the individual phases and the overall mechanical moduli L and M . Thus, we see that whatever information we have (from other sources) on the overall mechanical moduli immediately implies corresponding information on the thermal moduli, i.e. coefficients of expansion

and heat capacities. It is this feature which distinguishes a two-phase composite from a general n-phase composite. Let us now examine some implications of the above observation.

We first note that the overall stiffness tensor L occurs linearly in (19) and that the overall compliance tensor M occurs linearly in (20) and (21). Now the problem of determining bounds on L and M has received considerable attention in the literature. For an isotropic dispersion of spheres see particularly Hashin and Shtrikman (9), Hill (10) and Walpole (11). For unidirectional fibre reinforced composites see Hashin (12), Hill (13) and Walpole (14), while for unidirectional platelet reinforced composites and laminates see Walpole (14). Our present objectives are best met by referring to the work of Walpole (11,14) which contains the most general analysis of the mechanical bounding problem. When we examine Walpole's results, it is obvious that we can immediately substitute the known upper and lower bounds for L and M into (19) - (21) to obtain the corresponding bounds on \underline{m} , $s(\epsilon)$ and $s(\sigma)$.

A second approach in the mechanical theory is given by the self-consistent method. This method takes into account the shape of the inclusions and is discussed by Hill (10), Budiansky (15) and Walpole (11) for spherical inclusions, by Hill (16) and Walpole (14) for unidirectional fibre reinforced materials and by Walpole (14) for unidirectional platelet reinforced and laminated materials. When we substitute the self-consistent mechanical moduli into (19) - (21) we arrive at self-consistent predictions for the overall thermal moduli. We remark that the results so obtained are completely in accord with the results obtained by Budiansky (7) and Laws (5,6) for general n-phase composites. Let us now return specifically to the work of Walpole (11,14) where it is rigorously shown that for an isotropic dispersion of spheres and for unidirectional fibre reinforced materials that the self-consistent results lie between the Hashin-Shtrikman bounds. It follows that the self-consistent results for the overall thermoelastic moduli also lie between the corresponding bounds. Finally, in the case of uni-directional platelet reinforced and laminated composites Walpole (14) shows in the mechanical problem that both bounds and the self-consistent predictions coincide to yield precise formula for the overall moduli. The above discussion shows that this conclusion applies immediately to the overall thermal moduli.

Before we leave this general discussion, we recall two elementary results due to Hill (8), namely

$$c_1 L_1 + c_2 L_2 \geq L, \quad c_1 M_1 + c_2 M_2 \geq M.$$

Thus, from (19) and (21),

$$s(\epsilon) \geq c_1 s_1(\epsilon) + c_2 s_2(\epsilon), \quad s(\sigma) \leq c_1 s_1(\sigma) + c_2 s_2(\sigma).$$

Isotropic Phases

In order to avoid a multitude of suffices it is convenient to introduce the unit second order tensor $\underline{1}$ with components δ_{ij} . Thus, when each phase is isotropic we may write

$$L_1 \underline{\varepsilon}_1 = 2\mu_1 (\underline{\varepsilon}_1 - \frac{1}{3}(\text{tr } \underline{\varepsilon}_1)\underline{1}) + \kappa_1 (\text{tr } \underline{\varepsilon}_1)\underline{1}, \quad (22)$$

$$\underline{m}_1 = \alpha_1 \underline{1}, \quad (23)$$

where tr denotes the trace and where κ_1 , μ_1 , α_1 are respectively the bulk modulus, shear modulus and coefficient of linear expansion of phase 1. We use a similar notation for phase 2. From (22) and (23) we readily show that

$$M_1 \underline{\sigma}_1 = \frac{1}{2\mu_1} (\underline{\sigma}_1 - \frac{1}{3}(\text{tr } \underline{\sigma}_1)\underline{1}) + \frac{1}{9\kappa_1} (\text{tr } \underline{\sigma}_1)\underline{1},$$

$$\underline{l}_1 = L_1 \underline{m}_1 = 3\kappa_1 \alpha_1 \underline{1}.$$

With the help of these formula (20) reduces to

$$\underline{m} = \frac{\kappa_1 \alpha_1 - \kappa_2 \alpha_2}{\kappa_1 - \kappa_2} \underline{1} - \frac{3\kappa_1 \kappa_1 (\alpha_1 - \alpha_2)}{\kappa_1 - \kappa_2} M_1 \underline{1}. \quad (24)$$

To prepare the ground for the formulae for the heat capacities we introduce two mechanical parameters. First, let $\kappa(\sigma)$ be the overall bulk modulus when the composite is subject to uniform hydrostatic pressure. Thus, we put $\theta = 0$ and $\underline{\sigma} = -p\underline{1}$ in equation (11) to show that

$$\kappa(\sigma)^{-1} = \underline{1} \cdot M \underline{1}.$$

Second, let $\kappa(\varepsilon)$ be the overall bulk modulus when the composite is strained uniformly and with all the principal strains equal. Thus we put $\theta = 0$ and $\underline{\varepsilon} = \Delta \underline{1}$ in (5) and find that

$$\kappa(\varepsilon) = \frac{1}{9} \underline{1} \cdot L \underline{1}.$$

When the composite is isotropic, $\kappa(\varepsilon) = \kappa(\sigma) = \kappa$. With the help of the above definitions of $\kappa(\sigma)$ and $\kappa(\varepsilon)$ we can now show that formulae (19) and (21) reduce to the elegant forms

$$\theta_R^{-1}(s(\varepsilon) - c_1 s_1(\varepsilon) - c_2 s_2(\varepsilon)) = \frac{9(\kappa_1 \alpha_1 - \kappa_2 \alpha_2)^2}{(\kappa_1 - \kappa_2)^2} (c_1 \kappa_1 + c_2 \kappa_2 - \kappa(\varepsilon)), \quad (25)$$

$$\theta_R^{-1}(s(\sigma) - c_1 s_1(\sigma) - c_2 s_2(\sigma)) = \frac{9\kappa_1^2 \kappa_2^2 (\alpha_1 - \alpha_2)^2}{(\kappa_1 - \kappa_2)^2} \left(\frac{1}{\kappa(\sigma)} - \frac{c_1}{\kappa_1} - \frac{c_2}{\kappa_2} \right). \quad (26)$$

Isotropic Dispersion of Spheres

From an algebraic point of view, an isotropic dispersion of spheres is, perhaps, the simplest composite. In this case, we know that

$$\underline{\underline{m}} = \alpha \underline{\underline{1}},$$

$$M \underline{\underline{\sigma}} = \frac{1}{2\mu} (\underline{\underline{\sigma}} - \frac{1}{3}(\text{tr } \underline{\underline{\sigma}}) \underline{\underline{1}}) + \frac{1}{9\kappa} (\text{tr } \underline{\underline{\sigma}}) \underline{\underline{1}},$$

where κ , μ , α are respectively the overall bulk modulus, shear modulus and coefficient of linear expansion. Thus, formula (24) collapses to

$$\alpha = \frac{\kappa_1 \alpha_1 - \kappa_2 \alpha_2}{\kappa_1 - \kappa_2} - \frac{\kappa_1 \kappa_2 (\alpha_1 - \alpha_2)}{\kappa (\kappa_1 - \kappa_2)}. \quad (27)$$

Also, the overall heat capacities are given by (25) and (26) when $\kappa(\varepsilon)$ and $\kappa(\sigma)$ are replaced by κ . We remark that each of these formulae is independent of the shear modulus μ . The known formulae for the Hashin-Shtrikman bounds for κ may now be substituted into (27) to obtain the Hashin-Shtrikman bounds for α . Likewise, we can substitute the self-consistent predictions for κ into (28) to obtain the self-consistent estimate of α . Rather than write out these formulae at length, we exhibit a comparison of the various results in Figure 1. For the mechanical problem, the Hashin-Shtrikman bounds are given, e.g. in (9), (10) and (11) and the self-consistent predictions may be found in (10), (11) and (15). We note that the numerical results confirm the earlier prediction that the self-consistent results always lie between the Hashin-Shtrikman bounds.

Transversely isotropic materials

We now consider composite materials which are transversely isotropic with respect to the third cartesian axis Ox_3 . Such materials include unidirectional fibre reinforced materials with Ox_3 in the fibre direction and unidirectional platelet reinforced materials with Ox_3 normal to every platelet. The best notation for this problem is due to Hill (13). When L is transversely isotropic the equations $\sigma = L\epsilon$ may be written

$$\frac{1}{2}(\sigma_{11} + \sigma_{22}) = k(\epsilon_{11} + \epsilon_{22}) + \ell\epsilon_{33},$$

$$\sigma_{33} = \ell(\epsilon_{11} + \epsilon_{22}) + n\epsilon_{33},$$

$$\frac{1}{2}(\sigma_{11} - \sigma_{22}) = m(\epsilon_{11} - \epsilon_{22}),$$

$$\sigma_{23} = 2p\epsilon_{23}, \quad \sigma_{13} = 2p\epsilon_{13}.$$

Here k is the plane strain bulk modulus, m the transverse shear modulus, p the longitudinal shear modulus, n the modulus for longitudinal uniaxial straining and ℓ is the associated cross modulus. Following Walpole (14) we write $L = (2k, \ell, n, 2m, 2p)$. In this notation

$$M = (n/2kE, -\nu/E, 1/E, 1/2m, 1/2p),$$

where $E = n - \ell^2/k$ and $\nu = \ell/2k$ are respectively the conventional Young's modulus and Poisson's ratio under longitudinal load. In addition, we know that for transversely isotropic materials the tensor \underline{m} has only two independent components. More precisely, the only non-zero components are $m_{11} = m_{22} = \beta$, the coefficient of transverse linear expansion and $m_{33} = \gamma$, the coefficient of longitudinal linear expansion. With this notation it is easy to show that

$$\kappa(\sigma) = kE/(k + n - 2\ell), \quad \kappa(\epsilon) = (4k + 4\ell + n)/9. \quad (28)$$

We now have sufficient notation to read off the required results for the bounds and self-consistent estimates of the thermal moduli. The required formulae for the heat capacities are obtained by simple substitution of (28) into (25) and (26). Furthermore, equation (24) now yields two equations for the expansion coefficients β and γ :

$$\beta = \frac{\kappa_1\alpha_1 - \kappa_2\alpha_2}{\kappa_1 - \kappa_2} - \frac{3\kappa_1\kappa_2(\alpha_1 - \alpha_2)}{\kappa_1 - \kappa_2} \frac{n - \ell}{2kE}, \quad (29)$$

$$\gamma = \frac{\kappa_1 \alpha_1 - \kappa_2 \alpha_2}{\kappa_1 - \kappa_2} - \frac{3\kappa_1 \kappa_2 (\alpha_1 - \alpha_2) k - \ell}{\kappa_1 - \kappa_2} \cdot \frac{k - \ell}{kE}. \quad (30)$$

In the case of unidirectional fibre reinforced materials, the appropriate bounds for the mechanical problem are given in references (12), (13) and (14) and the self-consistent estimates may be found in (14) and (16). Again, we do not write down the relevant formulae at length, instead we present a comparison of the various results in Figure 2. Once more, we draw attention to the fact that the self-consistent method gives results which are intermediate to the various bounds. We emphasize that these results are only valid for continuous fibre-reinforcement or for materials with chopped fibres whose aspect ratios are large.

Finally we consider composites consisting of parallel continuous laminae or of parallel platelets whose aspect ratios are large. As indicated earlier, the significant feature of the mechanical problem for these composites is that both bounds coincide with the self-consistent result (14). The appropriate formulae are

$$\begin{aligned} 1/p &= c_1/p_1 + c_2/p_2, & 1/n &= c_1/n_1 + c_2/n_2, \\ m &= c_1 m_1 + c_2 m_2, & \ell/n &= c_1 \ell_1/n_1 + c_2 \ell_2/n_2, \\ k - \ell^2/n &= c_1 (k_1 - \ell_1^2/n_1) + c_2 (k_2 - \ell_2^2/n_2). \end{aligned}$$

We can now substitute these formulae into (29) and (30) to get explicit formulae for the overall coefficients of expansion, and into (28) and thence into (25) and (26) to get the overall heat capacities. The results are presented graphically in Figure 3.

Acknowledgement I wish to thank Messrs. G.R. Ben Abbas, B.T. Wells and T.I. Williams for help with the numerical work.

References

1. Levin, V.M., "On the Coefficients of Thermal Expansion of Heterogeneous Materials", Mekhanika Tverdogo Tela, 1967, pp 88-94.
2. Schapery, R.A., "Thermal Expansion Coefficients of Composite Materials Based on Energy Principles", Journal of Composite Materials, Vol.2, 1968, pp 380-404.

3. Rosen, B.W. and Hashin, Z., "Effective Thermal Expansion Coefficients and Specific Heats of Composite Materials", International Journal of Engineering Science, Vol.8, 1970, pp 157-173.
4. Hashin, Z., "Theory of Fibre Reinforced Materials", NASA CR-1974, March 1972.
5. Laws, N., "On the Thermostatics of Composite Materials", Journal of the Mechanics and Physics of Solids, Vol.21, 1973, pp 9-17.
6. Laws, N., "The Overall Thermoelastic Moduli of Transversely Isotropic Composites According to the Self-Consistent Method", International Journal of Engineering Science, Vol.12, 1974, pp 79-87.
7. Budiansky, B., "Thermal and Thermoelastic Properties of Isotropic Composites", Journal of Composite Materials, Vol.4, 1970, pp 286-295.
8. Hill, R., "Elastic Properties of Reinforced Solids: Some Theoretical Principles", Journal of the Mechanics and Physics of Solids, Vol.11, 1963, pp 357-372.
9. Hashin, Z. and Shtrikman, S., "A Variational Approach to the Theory of the Elastic Behaviour of Multiphase Materials", Journal of the Mechanics and Physics of Solids, Vol.11, 1963, pp 127-140.
10. Hill, R., "A Self-Consistent Mechanics of Composite Materials", Journal of the Mechanics and Physics of Solids, Vol.13, 1965, pp 213-222.
11. Walpole, L.J., "On Bounds for the Overall Elastic Moduli of Inhomogeneous Systems - I", Journal of the Mechanics and Physics of Solids, Vol.14, 1966, pp 151-162.
12. Hashin, Z., "On Elastic Behaviour of Fibre Reinforced Materials of Arbitrary Transverse Phase Geometry", Journal of the Mechanics and Physics of Solids, Vol.13, 1965, pp 119-134.
13. Hill, R., "Theory of Mechanical Properties of Fibre-Strengthened Materials: I. Elastic Behaviour", Journal of the Mechanics and Physics of Solids, Vol.12, 1964, pp 199-212.
14. Walpole, L.J., "On the Overall Elastic Moduli of Composite Materials", Journal of the Mechanics and Physics of Solids, Vol.17, 1969, pp 235-251.

15. Budiansky, B., "On the Elastic Moduli of Some Heterogeneous Materials", Journal of the Mechanics and Physics of Solids, Vol. 13, 1965, pp 223-227.
16. Hill, R., "Theory of Mechanical Properties of Fibre-Strengthened Materials - III. Self-Consistent Model", Journal of the Mechanics and Physics of Solids, Vol. 13, 1965, pp 189-198.

Fig. 1a Coefficient of expansion for isotropic dispersion of spheres.

Fig. 1b Heat capacity at constant stress for isotropic dispersion of spheres.

Fig. 1c Heat capacity at constant strain for isotropic dispersion of spheres.

Fig. 2a Transverse coefficient of expansion for fibre reinforced material.

Fig. 2b Longitudinal coefficient of expansion for fibre reinforced material.

Fig. 2c Heat capacity at constant stress for fibre reinforced material.

Fig. 2d Heat capacity at constant strain for fibre reinforced material.

Fig. 3a Transverse coefficient of expansion for platelet reinforced material.

Fig. 3b Longitudinal coefficient of expansion for platelet reinforced material.

Fig. 3c Heat capacity at constant stress for platelet reinforced material.

Fig. 3d Heat capacity at constant strain for platelet reinforced material.